

SYNTHESIS OF GADOLINIUM-BASED METAL-ORGANIC FRAMEWORKS AND THEIR ADSORPTION PERFORMANCE FOR FORMALDEHYDE

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ABSTRACT

As a major indoor volatile organic pollutant, formaldehyde can cause damage to multiple human systems and exhibit carcinogenicity upon long-term exposure. Gadolinium-based metal-organic frameworks (Gd-MOFs) constructed from lanthanide ions have emerged as promising MOF materials due to their structural diversity. This study focuses on the design, synthesis, and adsorption properties of Gd-MOFs. A series of gadolinium-based MOF materials were prepared via hydrothermal synthesis. Their structures were characterized using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) and X-ray powder diffraction (PXRD). The adsorption of formaldehyde by each as-synthesized material was monitored using a formaldehyde analyzer. In summary, this research synthesized and elucidated the adsorption characteristics of Gd-MOFs so as to develop efficient formaldehyde adsorbents, and

provide technical support for removing indoor formaldehyde pollution.

KEYWORDS: Formaldehyde; Metal-organic frameworks; Gadolinium.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indoor air plays a crucial role in human life quality. Volatile organic compounds (VOCs), as indoor pollutants, have attracted increasing attention. Among them, formaldehyde (HCHO) is one of the most representative, well-known, and common VOCs in indoor air pollution.^[1]

Numerous animal experiments and epidemiological data have shown that long-term exposure to formaldehyde can cause damage to the respiratory system,^[2] nervous system,^[3] immune system,^[4] reproductive system^[5], cardiovascular system^[6], and exhibit carcinogenic toxicity.^[7]

Metal-organic framework (MOF) is a class of porous materials with periodic three-dimensional network structures formed by the self-assembly of metal ions or metal clusters (commonly referred to as secondary building units, SBUs) and organic ligands through coordination bonds. In this self-assembly process, metal ions or metal clusters act as connection points, and organic ligands serve as linkers, which are tightly combined through coordination interactions to form stable porous structures. By carefully selecting metal ions,^[8,9,10,11] and organic ligands,^[12,13,14] the pore size, shape, and chemical environment of MOFs can be regulated.

Due to their ultra-high porosity, large specific surface area, and the ability to precisely control pore size, shape, topological structure, and excellent chemical stability by adjusting metal ions, organic ligands, and their connection modes, MOFs can function as "molecular containers" for adsorbing and immobilizing target molecules,^[15,16,17,18,19]

Currently, various MOF materials have been widely used in the field of environmental protection,^[20,21,22,23,24] Gadolinium (III) ions have a strong coordination ability with oxygen donors, while polycarboxylic acid ligands are rich in binding sites, and thus making them ideal ligands for constructing gadolinium-based metal-organic frameworks (Gd-MOFs). This study designs new formaldehyde adsorbents, which are expected to remove formaldehyde pollution in indoor environments.

2. Experiments

2.1 Experimental Materials and Instruments

Gadolinium (III) chloride (99.9%) was purchased from Leyan Chemicals; terephthalic acid (99.99%), 2-aminoterephthalic acid (98.57%), and 2,5-dihydroxyterephthalic acid (99.89%) were obtained from Bidepharm (Shanghai, China); formaldehyde (37wt%, with 10-15% methanol as stabilizer) was supplied by Shanghai Macklin Biochemical Technology Co., Ltd. (Shanghai, China); N,N'-dimethylformamide (analytical grade) was purchased from Guangdong Guanghua Technology Co., Ltd. Guangzhou, China); sodium hydroxide (analytical grade) was purchased from Tianjin Damao Chemical Reagent (Tianjin, China).

2.2 Synthesis of MOFs

All three gadolinium-based MOFs used in this study are in powder form.

Gd-BDC-NH₂: 905.75 mg H₂BDC-NH₂ (5 mmol) and 600 mg NaOH (15 mmol) were added into a conical flask, and dissolved in 50 mL H₂O, followed by transfer to a round-bottom flask (ligand solution). 1318.05 mg GdCl₃ (5 mmol) was dissolved in 50 mL H₂O. The GdCl₃ solution was added into the ligand solution using a dropping funnel, and stir at 200 r/min at room temperature. After the dropwise addition, the mixture was kept in a 120°C oil bath for 2 hours. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction product was purified by filtration, washed with H₂O three times, and dried to obtain Gd-BDC-NH₂ powder.

Gd-BDC: 830.7 mg H₂BDC (5 mmol) and 600 mg NaOH (15 mmol) were added into a conical flask, and dissolved in 50 mL H₂O, followed by transfer to a round-bottom flask (ligand solution). 1318.05 mg GdCl₃ (5 mmol) was dissolved in 50 mL H₂O. The GdCl₃ solution was added into the ligand solution using a dropping funnel, and stir at 200 r/min at room temperature. After the dropwise addition, the mixture was kept in a 120°C oil bath for 2 hours. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction product was purified by filtration, washed with H₂O three times, and dried to obtain Gd-BDC powder.

Gd-DHTA: 990.65 mg H₂DHTA (5 mmol) and 600 mg NaOH (15 mmol) were added into a conical flask, and dissolved in 50 mL H₂O, followed by transfer to a round-bottom flask (ligand solution). 1318.05 mg GdCl₃ (5 mmol) was dissolved in 50 mL H₂O. The GdCl₃ solution was added into the ligand solution using a dropping funnel, and stir at 200 r/min at room temperature. After the dropwise addition, the mixture was kept in a 120°C oil bath for 2 hours. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction product was purified by filtration, washed with H₂O three times, and dried to obtain Gd-DHTA powder.

2.3 Structural Characterization of MOFs

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) were used to characterize the three MOFs. Before characterization, the MOFs were dried in an oven at 100°C for 24 hours.

2.4 Determination of Formaldehyde Adsorption by MOFs

Formaldehyde adsorption experiments were conducted on the obtained MOFs, and the formaldehyde content was monitored with a formaldehyde analyzer.

Each MOF (1.0 g) was placed in a transparent glass petri dish. Formaldehyde aqueous solution (2 μL) was added in a 1.5 mL liquid-phase vial. Then, the petri dish containing MOF, vial containing formaldehyde, and formaldehyde analyzer was placed in a closed box (30 \times 40 \times 50 cm^3). The formaldehyde concentration was monitored for 30 min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Synthesis and Characterization of MOFs

MOFs were synthesized by hydrothermal reaction of Gd(III) with three carboxylic acid ligands (Figure 1) at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 hours.

Figure 1. Carboxylic acid ligands.

3.1.1 FT-IR Spectrum of Gd-BDC-NH₂

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy was used for the preliminary characterization of Gd-BDC-NH₂. As shown in Figure 2, the asymmetric stretching vibration of the carboxyl group in the MOF material Gd-BDC-NH₂ is at 1546 cm^{-1} , while that of the free carboxyl group is 1689 cm^{-1} , showing a significant shift, indicating that the carboxyl group has coordinated with gadolinium ions.

Figure 2. FT-IR spectra of Gd-BDC-NH₂ (upper) and H₂BDC-NH₂ (lower).

3.1.2 FT-IR Spectrum of Gd-DHTA

As shown in Figure 3, the asymmetric stretching vibration of the carboxyl group (C=O) in the MOF material Gd-DHTA is at 1588 cm^{-1} . Compared with the stretching vibration of the free carboxyl group (C=O) at 1648 cm^{-1} , there is a significant shift and a decrease in peak intensity, indicating coordination of the carboxyl group with gadolinium ions.

Figure 3. FT-IR spectra of Gd-DHTA (upper) and H₂DHTA (lower).

3.1.3 FT-IR Spectrum of Gd-BDC

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy was used for the preliminary characterization of Gd-BDC. As shown in Figure 4, the asymmetric stretching vibration of the carboxyl group (C=O) in Gd-BDC is at 1552 cm^{-1} . Compared with the stretching vibration of the free carboxyl group (C=O) at 1680 cm^{-1} , there is a significant shift, indicating that the coordination of carboxyl group with gadolinium ions.

Figure 4. FT-IR spectra of Gd-BDC (upper) and H₂BDC (lower)

3.1.4 Powder X-ray Diffraction Analysis of Gd-BDC-NH₂, Gd-DHTA, and Gd-BDC

Powder X-ray diffraction analysis was performed on Gd-BDC-NH₂, Gd-DHTA, and Gd-BDC (Figure 5). It can be seen that neither Gd-BDC-NH₂ nor Gd-DHTA has obvious diffraction peaks, indicating that both MOFs are amorphous powders. Gd-BDC has diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 6.0^\circ$, 29.5° , and 30.0° . So, the crystalline state of Gd-BDC is significantly better than those of the previous two MOFs.

Figure 5. PXRD patterns of (a) Gd-BDC-NH₂; (b) Gd-DHTA; (c) Gd-BDC.

3.2 Formaldehyde Adsorption by MOFs

Formaldehyde adsorption tests were carried out on the three as-synthesized MOFs (Gd-BDC-NH₂, Gd-BDC, and Gd-DHTA) (Figure 6). It can be seen that all three MOFs exhibit obvious adsorption capacity as compared with the control group.

Figure 6. Formaldehyde concentrations at 0, 3, 9, 18, 24 and 30 min. Notably, the adsorption capacity of Gd-DHTA (at 3 min, 9 min, 18 min, 24 min, and 30 min) is higher than those of the other two materials.

The reason may be that the hydroxyl groups (—OH) on the ligand can form hydrogen bonds with the oxygen atoms in formaldehyde, and the hydrogen atoms on formaldehyde can also form secondary hydrogen bonds with the oxygen atoms on the hydroxyl groups, achieving a "double hydrogen bond" synergistic driving effect.^[25,26]

4. CONCLUSIONS

MOFs have high microporosity, well-defined structures and tunable functions, showing great potential in solving air pollution problems. The introduction of open metal sites to enhance interactions with target gases has been proven to be an effective strategy for capturing toxic gases. In this study, three different Gd-MOFs were successfully developed and applied to formaldehyde removal, and the results showed that all of them have obvious effects. Our research results also indicate that the absorption of formaldehyde can be enhanced through intermolecular interactions by introducing functionalized groups (such as hydroxyl groups) on the pore walls of MOFs.

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